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Mob censorship as a new challenge for journalists: Evidence from Kosovo

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the impact of mob censorship on journalists' professional practices and emotional well-being. Emerging within the last five years, mob censorship refers to the mobilization of online publics—often fueled by social media, political polarization, and populist discourse—to harass, delegitimize, and silence journalists. Kosovo serves as a particularly relevant case, being the first European country without daily print newspapers, highly politically polarized, and a highly digitized country with internet usage above the EU average. Using a qualitative approach, the study draws on semi-structured interviews with journalists and editors across diverse professional contexts. The findings demonstrate that mob censorship constitutes a pervasive form of political and societal pressure, enacted primarily through social media platforms where harassment, defamation, and threats function as tools of symbolic control. Unlike traditional top-down censorship, mob censorship operates as a bottom-up mechanism, with digital publics exerting influence through normative judgment and moral condemnation. Consequently, journalists increasingly engage in self-censorship, driven by fear and emotional fatigue, posing significant risks to press freedom and undermining their psychological well-being.

1. Introduction

Contemporary journalism operates in an environment where digital platforms have profoundly reshaped how information is produced and distributed. Social media have become central channels for reporting and information circulation (Jamil, 2020) and are now embedded in journalists' daily routines and professional norms (Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023). As a result, the structure of information flow has shifted—from traditional top-down, “waterfall” communication toward more horizontal forms of interaction, and from mass communication to communication mediated by social media platforms (Livingstone, 2015).

At the same time, social media have transformed the relationship between journalists and the public. These platforms increasingly influence journalists' ability to connect with audiences, publish stories, and cultivate sources (Waisbord, 2020; Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023). Individuals now act as media actors in their own right, creating and circulating information and interacting in real time with wide audiences (Kim, 2021). While this direct interaction opens new spaces for communication, it also exposes journalists to new forms of pressure, intimidation, and public delegitimization (Brown et al., 2022; Reporters Without Borders, 2024; Xin, 2024). In these highly participatory

communication settings, the entire public takes part. This dynamic enhances opportunities for civic engagement but also intensifies online competition for attention and credibility—particularly among political actors (Vaccari & Valeriani, 2021). As Eco (2015) polemically notes, “social media give legions of idiots the same right to speak as a Nobel Prize winner”. When information contradicts public preferences, digital platforms become arenas of opposition and attacks against journalists and dissenting voices, often aiming to silence them (Waisbord, 2020). Such developments pose significant threats to press freedom, journalistic safety, and the overall quality of democratic discourse (Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023; Reporters Without Borders, 2024).

These trends have intensified markedly over the past decade with the expansion of social media platforms, which facilitate unprecedented levels of direct and instantaneous public engagement with journalists through comments, private messages, emails, and other interactive channels (Jamil, 2020; Sinclair et al., 2025; Waisbord, 2020). Notably, this phenomenon is not confined to authoritarian contexts but is increasingly evident within democratic societies as well (Lee et al., 2023; Löfgren & Örnebring, 2016; Zelizer, 2023).

Within this shifting digital landscape, scholars have begun to conceptualize a relatively new form of pressure on journalists: mob censorship. Systematically developed by Waisbord (2020, 2023), mob

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ensorship refers to bottom-up pressure exerted by digital mobs through coordinated harassment, public discrediting, and moral or ideological intimidation. In contrast to traditional, top-down forms of censorship imposed by states or institutional authorities, mob censorship emerges from the public itself and materializes through sustained harassment, threats, and other forms of online aggression. This phenomenon undermines journalists' professional autonomy, distorts reporting quality, and adversely affects their well-being.

Despite increasing scholarly attention to online harassment and traditional top-down censorship, research specifically examining bottom-up forms of censorship—commonly referred to as mob censorship—remains limited. This is primarily because the concept has only recently been consolidated in the literature (Waisbord, 2020, 2023; Zelizer, 2023). Distinctively, mob censorship relies on digitally orchestrated, militant online collectives—often explicitly mobilized or implicitly sanctioned by political actors—to exert coercive pressure on journalists with the aim of delegitimizing and ultimately silencing critical reporting. Such campaigns are often instigated or amplified by political elites, and at times arise spontaneously, though still fueled by intolerant political discourse (Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023).

Therefore, expanding empirical knowledge on mob censorship, as undertaken in this paper, is essential—particularly in democratic contexts such as Kosovo, where networked publics increasingly function as coercive actors. Kosovo represents a distinctive case: the first European country to discontinue print newspaper circulation, the only European country to experience a government collapse at the height of the Covid-19 pandemic, and a highly politically polarized society. These developments have transformed the country's media landscape into a highly digitized and contested environment, rendering it particularly susceptible to bottom-up digital pressures.

Against this backdrop, the present study explores how mob censorship operates in Kosovo and examines its implications for journalists' professional autonomy, newsroom practices, emotional well-being, and the mechanisms available to mitigate such pressures within a highly networked and politically polarized environment.

The analysis is guided by the following research questions:

1. What forms and dynamics of mob censorship and online harassment do journalists in Kosovo currently experience?
2. Which individual and editorial strategies do journalists employ to cope with or navigate these pressures?
3. How does mob censorship shape journalists' emotional and psychological well-being?
4. What gender-specific patterns characterize mob censorship, and how do they influence the professional experiences of women journalists?

Together, these questions provide the analytical framework through which the study explores mob censorship as a communicative and socio-political phenomenon within the contemporary Kosovar media landscape.

The remainder of the paper situates the study within broader scholarly debates on journalism's democratic role and the pressures that undermine it. It then turns to traditional forms of state-imposed censorship before tracing the shift toward digitally mediated, bottom-up pressures conceptualized as mob censorship. Building on this foundation, the paper explains why Kosovo provides a particularly relevant case for investigating this phenomenon. The subsequent sections outline the qualitative methodology, present the findings across four thematic categories, and conclude by discussing the broader theoretical and practical implications of the study.

2. Literature review

2.1. The role and responsibilities of journalists

Traditionally, journalism and its professional values have held a

central role in democratic societies (Deuze, 2005). Scholars and practitioners generally identify two core duties of journalism: the pursuit of truth and loyalty to citizens (Kovach & Rosenstiel, 2021; Tandoc et al., 2022). Fulfilling these duties requires independent and ethical practice, with journalists prioritizing truth, autonomy, and public service, and ensuring that news is relevant, timely, and responsibly reported (Saliu et al., 2024; Saliu, 2025; Anderson et al., 2016; Brooks et al., 2014). This is often achieved through disseminator journalism, which involves both delivering news and interpreting societal events. Accurate and reliable reporting enhances public awareness of propaganda and misinformation (Acerbi et al., 2022), enabling citizens to engage in informed, critical debate (Coudry et al., 2010).

In a context of symmetrical communication, citizens interact directly with journalists via social media, but these platforms also facilitate the spread of misinformation, disinformation, and fake news, often accompanied by online abuse (Aïmeur et al., 2023). Such abuse can escalate into offline harassment, including verbal insults, threats, or physical violence (Miller, 2025). Online harassment produces comparable psychological and professional effects and can mobilize others—even anonymously or from abroad—to target journalists (Harlow et al., 2023; Relly, 2021). These pressures present a significant challenge for journalism, contributing to censorship and undermining both the pursuit of truth and public trust in the media.

2.2. Censorship: state control of information

Censorship is not a new phenomenon; it predates modern states and has appeared throughout history in diverse forms. In the 17th century, John Milton's *Areopagitica* (1644) famously opposed censorship, specifically challenging the English licensing system that restricted the free flow of ideas (Milton, 2008). In the 20th century, authoritarian regimes such as Nazi Germany, the Soviet Union, and communist governments in Eastern Europe institutionalized strict media censorship, fully controlling public discourse to consolidate state power. Historically, censorship has operated through multiple mechanisms, including direct governmental intervention, corporate influence, and internal editorial decisions, often culminating in self-censorship within media organizations (McChesney, 2015). Such interventions significantly limit journalism's capacity to report objectively and critically on issues of public interest (Ruge, 2018).

Broadly defined, media censorship encompasses both formal and informal restrictions on journalists' and media outlets' ability to collect, disseminate, and interpret information—a right protected under Article 19 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Corduneanu-Huci & Hamilton, 2022). Not all censorship is externally imposed; journalists frequently engage in self-censorship, withholding or modifying information not due to direct prohibition but out of fear of social backlash, professional sanctions, or political repercussions (Lee et al., 2023; Yuen & Lee, 2025).

Media censorship typically manifests in two primary forms. First, pre-publication censorship, a top-down mechanism, occurs when state authorities, political actors, business elites, or other powerful interests intervene to prevent news from reaching the public, blocking potentially threatening information before publication (Schauer, 1978). Second, post-publication censorship, also top-down, involves punitive measures applied after publication, including threats, intimidation, verbal attacks, smear campaigns, or strategic lawsuits against public participation (SLAPP), aimed at curbing critical reporting (Lanoszka, 2021).

Even in democratic societies, censorship persists in subtler forms. Economic pressures, advertising dependencies, and concentrated media ownership often lead journalists and outlets to suppress or avoid topics that could challenge financial or political interests (Besley & Prat, 2006; Herman & Chomsky, 2002; Bourdieu, 1998). With the rise of the internet, censorship has expanded to digital mechanisms such as government surveillance, online content moderation, website blocking, and harassment of journalists and activists (Zelizer, 2023). These practices

are increasingly observed in Western democracies through strategies including information suppression, covert editorial changes, and platform-based moderation (Carlson et al., 2021; Meserve & Pemstein, 2018; Nechushtai, 2023).

The effects of censorship are not always immediate or overt. Anticipating potential threats, retaliation, or other risks, journalists may engage in self-censorship to mitigate dangers. Over time, this practice undermines the professionalism, independence, and objectivity of journalistic reporting.

2.2.1. Self-censorship

Noelle-Neumann (1974) was among the first to theorize this phenomenon through the concept of the *spiral of silence*, arguing that individuals are less likely to express opinions they perceive as unpopular for fear of social isolation. This silence reinforces dominant narratives while silencing minority viewpoints, shaping public discourse not solely through reasoned argument, but through social pressure and fear (Noelle-Neumann, 1974, 1977; Noelle-Neumann & Petersen, 2004).

While initially conceptualized in a pre-digital context, the spiral of silence is arguably more pronounced in the age of social media. When journalists or individuals perceive that their opinions diverge from the online majority, they may choose silence over expression, particularly in public digital forums. This dynamic affects both content creators and consumers. On social media, users often share content that aligns with dominant or partisan narratives, intensifying polarization and increasing the visibility of ideologically extreme news (Tsftati et al., 2013). Platforms such as X (formerly Twitter) and Facebook, while central to digital journalism, have also become arenas for hate speech and harassment. Despite moderation efforts, inconsistent enforcement and regulatory gaps allow toxic discourse to persist (Stockmann et al., 2023; Wang & Kim, 2023).

Lee (1998) defines journalistic self-censorship as “a set of editorial actions ranging from omission, dilution, distortion, change of emphasis, or choice of rhetorical devices by journalists, their organizations, and even the entire media community, in anticipation of currying reward and avoiding punishment from the power structure” (p. 57). This conceptualization underscores that self-censorship is not merely an individual response but often a collective and institutionalized practice, shaping the content, framing, and scope of journalistic reporting.

2.3. Mob censorship

2.3.1. The new communication ecosystem

With the rise of the internet—and especially social media—the public has increasingly migrated online. Alongside an internet-native generation, we now see the emergence of the “medium individual” (Kim, 2021), and even the traditional public sphere has shifted to platforms such as Facebook, a transformation some describe as “Facebook democracy” (Marichal, 2012). Social media offers journalists expanded opportunities not only to disseminate information but also to engage directly with audiences (Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023). At the same time, these platforms empower users as both receivers and producers of information, intensifying direct and immediate interactions with journalists through comments, messages, emails, and other digital forums (Jamil, 2020; Sinclair et al., 2025; Waisbord, 2020).

However, the same interactive environments have increasingly become arenas for attacks against journalists. In recent years, individuals and political actors—including those in democratic societies—have escalated online hostility, using insults, discrediting narratives, and direct threats to delegitimize the press (Brown et al., 2022; Reporters Without Borders, 2024; Xin, 2024). Political and ideological polarization further amplifies hate speech and exclusionary rhetoric, especially on platforms like Facebook (Kalsnes & Ihlebæk, 2021; Ghasiya & Sasahara, 2022). These dynamics are exacerbated by the growing interaction between populist governments and online militants, contributing to increasingly toxic political discourse (Fuller,

2018; Van Dalen, 2019; Waisbord, 2020). Such discourse not only marginalizes dissenting voices but also fosters emotional detachment, social prejudice, and, in extreme cases, incitement to violence against journalists (Abuín-Vences et al., 2022).

2.3.2. The emergence of bottom-up censorship

This convergence between online mobs and governmental actors has produced a novel form of censorship, often termed bottom-up censorship or mob censorship. In this model, militant online collectives—frequently instigated, encouraged, or amplified by political and corporate actors—actively seek to silence critical journalists in order to shield public figures or institutions that enjoy popular support (Waisbord, 2020, 2023). Unlike traditional protests aimed at those in power, mob censorship targets journalists directly. It constitutes an emergent form of digitally coordinated coercion that capitalizes on emotionally charged and polarized online environments.

While harassment has long existed both offline and online, mob censorship is distinctive because it highlights deliberate attempts by governments and corporations to incite or mobilize online mobs to target and silence journalists. The concept was systematically introduced by Silvio Waisbord (2020) and has since gained traction through scholarly debate and empirical work, most notably in a 2023 Digital Journalism special issue devoted entirely to mob censorship. Waisbord (2023) emphasizes that mob censorship must be understood within specific national and local contexts shaped by political, technological, and cultural dynamics.

Waisbord conceptualizes mob censorship as widespread and coordinated harassment of journalists by online users—often ordinary citizens—who engage in bottom-up acts of censorship designed to silence dissenting voices (Neilson & Ortiga, 2023; Waisbord, 2020, 2023). Although these actions appear spontaneous or grassroots, they are frequently embedded within broader political strategies in which governments, political elites, and partisan media legitimize hostility toward the press. These actors deploy harmful rhetoric, legal persecution, and delegitimizing narratives to demonize journalists and create favorable conditions for digital harassment (Waisbord, 2023; Malcorps et al., 2023). Thus, mob censorship is less an expression of spontaneous public anger than an extension of elite-driven campaigns that rely on social media platforms to amplify and normalize intimidation.

2.3.3. Role of governments and political actors

The role of governments is central to this process. Mob censorship is rarely a spontaneous mobilization of online users; rather, it is typically orchestrated or encouraged by state and corporate actors who incite and mobilize online supporters to target journalists. At minimum, their populist discourse fuels online militants. For example, one case documented by Henrichsen and Shelton (2023) describes a government encouraging supporters to dox a journalist on social media. As Waisbord (2023) succinctly argues, “mob censorship is linked to persistent efforts by governments and political elites to demonize, dehumanize, and persecute journalists through various tactics, namely, harmful rhetoric, legal instruments, and physical violence” (p. 1762).

In both authoritarian and democratic settings, digitally networked citizens engage in what Waisbord (2020) calls “bottom-up citizen vigilantism aimed at disciplining and silencing journalists” (p. 1031). These actions are fueled by populist narratives framing the press as “the enemy”, legitimizing online aggression in the name of political loyalty or moral righteousness. Mob censorship commonly manifests through coordinated use of bots, troll armies, fake accounts, and propaganda-driven media outlets, all of which aim to discredit journalists and instill fear (Waisbord, 2023). Central to this phenomenon is the goal of pushing journalists into self-censorship—forcing them to consider potential risks to their safety, their mental well-being, and the well-being of colleagues and family members.

Mob censorship thrives particularly within toxic digital cultures cultivated by right-wing and far-right communities, often reinforced by

populist authorities (Waisbord, 2018; Van Dalen, 2019). In the U.S. context, Waisbord (2020) identifies three main conditions enabling online harassment: the ease of direct access to journalists via social media, the normalization of toxic online discourse, and the political demonization of mainstream media. Within these environments, individuals and coordinated groups harass journalists on platforms such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), and TikTok, often propelled by algorithmic systems that reward high-engagement content—particularly outrage and polarization (Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023).

2.3.4. Consequences for journalists

The consequences of mob censorship are profound. Journalists subjected to persistent harassment report severe psychological and emotional distress, including anxiety, fear, and trauma (Miller, 2025). These experiences are often intensified by feelings of isolation, inadequate institutional support, and concerns that reporting attacks may harm their professional reputation (Waisbord, 2020, 2023). As a result, many engage in defensive strategies such as reducing online interaction, filtering messages, avoiding contentious topics, or modifying their reporting practices—clear indicators of self-censorship shaped by external coercion.

The impact extends beyond individual journalists to the broader newsroom environment. Editorial decisions increasingly reflect concerns about potential backlash, narrowing the diversity of perspectives and discouraging coverage of sensitive issues. In some cases, mob censorship may even affect recruitment, as newsrooms avoid hiring individuals who are likely targets of harassment or who specialize in high-risk topics (Miller, 2025; Waisbord, 2023). In this way, mob censorship functions as a mechanism of symbolic and structural control, blurring the boundaries between state repression and popular coercion in the digital age.

Ultimately, both top-down censorship—exerted by states, political elites, or powerful societal groups—and bottom-up mob censorship—driven by militant online attacks or state-instigated harassment—contribute to self-censorship among journalists, raising further concerns regarding their safety, autonomy, and freedom to report.

2.4. Empirical studies on mob censorship

The concept of mob censorship is relatively new in journalism studies, first introduced by Waisbord (2020) and later consolidated in a special issue of *Digital Journalism* in December 2023. Given its recent theoretical formalization, empirical studies that explicitly examine mob censorship remain limited. By contrast, there is a substantial and expanding body of research on the online harassment of journalists, particularly regarding its emotional, professional, and gendered consequences (e.g., Celuch et al., 2023; Holton et al., 2023; Jamil, 2020; Kim & Shin, 2025; Sinclair et al., 2025). Although the special issue dedicated to mob censorship includes twelve articles, not all of them are empirical; several are primarily theoretical. Nonetheless, a number of contributions offer qualitative analyses of mob censorship across diverse contexts and fields of study. Claesson (2023), for example, investigates mob-driven harassment of journalists in the United Kingdom and India, with a focus on the gendered dimensions of online violence and the structural constraints that shape journalists' responses to such attacks. The study highlights how newsroom environments often limit opportunities to address gender-based digital harassment effectively.

Similarly, Harlow et al. (2023), drawing on focus group discussions with Latin American journalists, examine how social media violence shapes journalistic work. These orchestrated attacks blur the boundary between citizen dissent and state-sponsored censorship.

Henrichsen and Shelton (2023), through semi-structured interviews with journalists, further demonstrate that online attacks are often amplified—or even initiated—by corporate actors, governments, and state-affiliated organizations. These dynamics illustrate that mob

censorship is not merely a grassroots phenomenon, but a technologically facilitated and strategically deployed form of coercion that undermines press freedom and democratic discourse.

However, the perception and meaning of mob censorship differ across cultural and national contexts. Malcorps et al. (2023) analyze how Belgian media managers define and interpret online harassment as mob censorship, revealing inconsistencies in recognizing such abuse and a lack of coordinated institutional responses—particularly when journalists who are women or members of minority groups are targeted.

Gender emerges as a central dimension in mob censorship research. Walulya and Selnes (2023) show how Ugandan women journalists experience and respond to harassment on social media, highlighting the intersection of gender and digital violence. Their study demonstrates that women face disproportionate levels of hostility, often characterized by moralizing or sexualized attacks. In an academic context, Nicolini and Filak (2022) find that mob censorship and self-censorship are more prevalent among female journalism students than their male counterparts.

Research in smaller media systems reflects similar patterns. Ivask (2025), examining the Estonian context through interviews with journalists, finds that harassment frequently stems from organized and anonymous online groups seeking to silence coverage of controversial or politically sensitive issues. These findings highlight the strategic and coordinated nature of such attacks, which are less expressions of spontaneous dissent than deliberate attempts to shape the news agenda.

Taken together, this emerging body of literature provides a more nuanced understanding of mob censorship as a distinct form of digital oppression. Although still under-theorized—particularly in non-Western and smaller media systems—current research underscores the urgency of further empirical investigation into the intersections between digital harassment, political polarization, and press freedom.

To provide a clear overview of these concepts and their key dimensions, Table 1 summarizes the most important concepts related to censorship and mob censorship identified in the literature.

2.5. Kosovo as a case study

Kosovo presents a particularly relevant case for studying mob censorship due to its high level of political polarization, intense online engagement, and rapid transformations within its media landscape. The European Commission, which annually evaluates Western Balkan countries aspiring to join the European Union, issued a more negative assessment of freedom of expression in Kosovo in its 2025 report than for other countries in the region (Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, North Macedonia, and Serbia). Of these six countries, only Albania and Kosovo were specifically identified for “intimidation of journalists.” Albania reported 45 cases of threats and intimidation (European Commission, 2025a), while Kosovo reported 70 cases involving physical or verbal attacks and threats (European Commission, 2025b). The report further noted that, during the electoral campaign, “high-ranking Kosovo officials, including the Prime Minister, used offensive language towards the media” (European Commission, 2025b, p. 35). Such attacks have been consistently condemned by professional associations of journalists, both local and international (European Federation of Journalists, 2023; AGK, 2023).

Persistent tensions between Kosovo and Serbia—aggravated by the absence of a formal peace agreement—continue to shape domestic political discourse. In this polarized environment, party militants and political actors frequently target critical journalists, accusing them of “serving Serbian interests in Kosovo”. These accusations not only delegitimize investigative journalists and independent commentators but also undermine their credibility as information sources, especially given the enduring collective memory of the 1999 war. Moreover, Russian propaganda has circulated in Kosovo through Serbian media channels, contributing to broader regional disinformation campaigns (European Commission, 2025b).

Table 1

Key concepts on censorship and mob censorship.

Concept	Definition/Description	Key Insights
Media Censorship	State or corporate control of information	Includes pre- and post-publication restrictions; limits journalistic independence; encourages self-censorship
Self-Censorship	Voluntary withholding or altering of content due to fear of consequences	Undermines journalistic objectivity and professional practices
Spiral of Silence	Avoiding expression of unpopular opinions to prevent social isolation	Amplified online; contributes to polarization and suppression of minority voices
Mob Censorship	Coordinated online harassment of journalists, often instigated by governments or corporations	Causes bottom-up censorship; induces fear, self-censorship, and professional limitations
Online Harassment	Hate speech, doxxing, trolling, threats, and reputational attacks	Affects journalists' mental health and reporting; politically or ideologically motivated

Source: Compiled by the author from existing literature.

The country's media ecosystem has also undergone significant structural shifts. Since April 2020, Kosovo has been the first country in Europe without a printed daily newspaper (Saliu et al., 2024). By 2025, 96.4% of households had access to high-speed internet—well above the European average of 85.8% (Eurostat, 2025). Additionally, at the height of the Covid-19 pandemic, on March 25, 2020, Kosovo became the first country in Europe—and possibly the world—to vote to oust its government due to deep inter-party polarization (Friedrich Naumann Foundation for Freedom, 2020).

Taken together, these factors make Kosovo an especially intriguing case for studying mob censorship, as it sits at the intersection of rapid digital adoption, intense political polarization, and a media landscape in flux.

3. Methodology/research design

3.1. Participants/sample

This study employs a qualitative research design based on in-depth, semi-structured interviews to explore the professional and emotional impact of mob censorship on journalists in Kosovo. Semi-structured interviews are particularly suited for this inquiry as they allow for the collection of rich, descriptive accounts grounded in the lived experiences of participants, rather than abstract theorizing (Denzin & Lincoln, 2017). This approach is especially relevant for examining issues such as self-censorship, emotional labor, and coping mechanisms, where nuance and depth are essential (Nelson & Tandoc, 2019). The choice of mixed data collection settings (face-to-face and online) was vital, acknowledging that gender and the study setting can act as determinants of research participation proclivity in sensitive topics (Gever, 2025).

As existing research has shown, the perception of journalistic identity—shaped by expectations regarding personality, integrity, and professional ideals—plays a key role in how journalists navigate harassment and pressure (Ferrer-Conill & Tandoc, 2018). Similar to prior studies of online harassment and mob censorship (e.g., Claesson, 2023; Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023; Ivask, 2025; Malcorps et al., 2023; Sinclair et al., 2025; Walulya & Selnes, 2023), this research adopts a qualitative framework to capture these complex dynamics.

A purposive sample of 17 journalists and editors was selected based on two criteria. The first group comprised nine journalists/editors who had publicly reported online harassment, providing access to well-documented experiences. The second group included eight journalists/editors covering sensitive topics—such as corruption, the judiciary, and gender rights—associated with increased exposure to online attacks. Participants included investigative journalists, reporters, and several individuals in editorial offices holding the dual status recognized in Kosovo as both journalist and editor. They worked across television and online media, with the latter coded as Digital Journalists, given the absence of print newspapers in Kosovo.

Of the 17 participants, 13 were men and four were women. This distribution does not reflect the overall gender composition of journalists in Kosovo, where women constitute approximately 65% of the profession (AGK, 2023). The selection was determined by the criteria

described above, and due to the refusal of three female journalists to participate, additional male journalists were included to complete the sample.

3.2. Informed consent

All participants gave their informed consent for inclusion before taking part in the study. Prior to their involvement, all interviewees were provided with clear and comprehensive explanations regarding the purpose and nature of the research. They were informed that participation was entirely voluntary, that the interviews would remain anonymous, and that their responses would be used solely for the purposes of this study.

3.3. Data collection procedures

The interviews were conducted during the summer of 2025. Face-to-face interviews were prioritized for less experienced journalists to foster rapport, while more experienced participants were interviewed via secure online platforms. Five senior journalists opted to respond via email, preferring the written format due to the sensitivity of the topic. Each interview lasted between 45 and 90 min and was transcribed verbatim. Special attention was given to paralinguistic cues—pauses, hesitations, changes in intonation—that indicated emotional distress, consistent with methodologies used in studies such as Sinclair et al. (2025).

The interview guide was structured according to a gradual-progression strategy frequently used in research on sensitive experiences. The interviews began with broad, non-intrusive questions about participants' professional background and everyday digital practices. Once rapport was established, the discussion moved to factual descriptions of online harassment they had encountered—used as an entry point because participants usually narrate these incidents in concrete, less emotionally taxing terms. Only after this foundation did the guide introduce topics that typically evoke stronger emotional responses, including coordinated attacks or mob censorship, peer pressure from colleagues, and the personal emotional impact of sustained hostility. The final stage of the interview addressed self-censorship and editorial or organizational responses, as these topics required participants to critically reflect on their own vulnerability and workplace dynamics, an area often perceived as sensitive. This staged design aimed to minimize emotional burden and build trust throughout the interview, in line with ethical recommendations in research on digital violence against journalists (Claesson, 2023).

3.4. Data analysis

Data analysis followed Braun and Clarke's (2012) thematic analysis framework. In the first phase, open coding was applied to the interview transcripts. Initial codes captured participants' experiences and meanings, such as "self-censorship – hesitation to publish" for the statement "I thought twice before publishing the article", or "institutional normalization of harassment" for "the editors told me not to take it seriously,

that it is part of the job". Other codes reflected avoidance of sensitive topics due to fear of online attacks and the psychological effects of harassment, highlighting the diversity of participants' experiences.

In the second phase, a constant comparison method was used to refine the coding scheme. Data segments were compared across interviews to identify patterns, consistencies, and contradictions. Some participants described self-censorship as a temporary survival tactic, while others viewed it as an internalized limitation on journalistic work. Codes were revised, merged, or clarified to ensure consistency and comprehensiveness.

In the final phase, codes were organized into four main themes: (1) the nature of harassment against journalists, (2) personal and editorial strategies in response to mob censorship, (3) impact on emotional and psychological well-being, and (4) gendered dimensions of mob censorship. Each theme was illustrated with direct quotations to accurately represent participants' perspectives. For example, the statement "I refused to pursue a corruption case because I was afraid of the comment campaign" was categorized under Theme 3, highlighting how fear affects emotional and psychological well-being and undermines investigative reporting.

As researchers with direct media experience, we remained attentive to potential biases and prioritized faithfully representing participants' accounts.

3.5. Theoretical framework for thematic interpretation

Thematic interpretations were grounded in the theoretical framework of mob censorship as a form of bottom-up pressure (Waisbord, 2020). For instance, the theme of self-censorship was analyzed as a defensive response to persistent online hostility, while the lack of editorial support was linked to structural failings within newsrooms, echoing Claesson's (2023) findings on institutional abandonment. The gendered analysis drew on literature showing how women and minority journalists disproportionately experience identity-based harassment (Walulya & Selnes, 2023).

Beyond individual experiences, the analysis also explored broader structural implications—how mob censorship shapes newsroom dynamics, curtails journalistic autonomy, and alters the relationship between journalists and the public. This approach aligns with the growing body of scholarship that frames online harassment not only as a personal threat but as a systemic challenge to press freedom and democratic discourse (Miller, 2022; Ivask, 2025).

4. Results

This section presents the key findings from semi-structured interviews with journalists and editors, highlighting both recurring patterns and individual variations in their experiences. The semi-structured format allowed participants to elaborate on their encounters with mob censorship, providing in-depth and nuanced insights into its manifestations, consequences, and coping strategies. The results are organized around four interrelated themes.

4.1. The nature of harassment against journalists

Journalists interviewed for this study consistently identified politically organized online mobs as the most frequent and damaging sources of harassment. In several cases, participants reported that party militants or ideologically aligned groups were mobilized to discredit critical reporting or suppress coverage of politically sensitive issues, such as corruption or extremism. Facebook and TikTok emerged as the most problematic platforms, due to their algorithmic reach and the ease with which "comment brigades" could be orchestrated.

Harassment typically begins in the comment sections of articles or videos and then escalates to private messages or phone calls. Attacks are often ideological or moralizing in nature and appear to be part of

coordinated campaigns driven by political partisans or groups with extremist religious agendas. "When reporting on sensitive affairs or issues of religious extremism, that's when attacks become coordinated and take on a political and ideological tone" (TV Journalist 2).

The forms of harassment are varied and include insults, defamatory claims, threats, and the manipulation of personal data. Several journalists reported being victims of "doxing", defined as the publication of personal information—such as home addresses or family details—on hostile online forums. In more extreme cases, offensive photo montages, altered images, and personal photographs were employed as tools of psychological intimidation.

Female journalists reported significantly different forms of harassment, primarily rooted in gender-based and sexualized attacks. These included derogatory comments about physical appearance, objectification, and insinuations regarding morality. "They called me a witch, ugly, bad-toothed, blind ... It's always about how you look, not what you report" (Investigative Journalist 1).

In contrast, male journalists were predominantly targeted with political epithets such as "Serbian mercenaries" or "atheists," reflecting ideological hostility rather than personal or gendered attacks.

4.2. Personal and editorial strategies in response to mob censorship

Journalists and editors described a range of personal coping mechanisms employed to manage the emotional toll of online harassment. Many adopted strategies of emotional distancing, such as avoiding social media comments or selectively filtering content. "In most cases, I don't read the comments at all—only to get a sense of the audience's mood. I try not to waste energy on thousands of hateful reactions. If something serious happens, I report it to the police" (Digital Journalist 4).

While these personal strategies provided some psychological relief, they largely represent individualized responses to a structural problem. Institutional responses, by contrast, were described as inconsistent or entirely absent. Although newsrooms sometimes served as spaces of emotional solidarity—"we support each other"—they rarely offered formal mechanisms for legal assistance, psychological support, or editorial protection. "We have a lawyer in the newsroom, but no training or support structure. Those things are handled by the Journalists' Association, not the media outlet" (Digital Journalist 1).

Most responses to mob censorship were reported as ad hoc, improvised, and largely limited to informal support among colleagues. There were also accounts of editorially driven self-censorship, where journalists were explicitly discouraged from pursuing certain stories: "I was told not to broadcast a certain investigative piece to avoid escalating threats" (Investigative Journalist 5).

Although no journalist explicitly admitted to abandoning a story entirely due to threats, all acknowledged some degree of hesitation or editorial restraint:

"I thought twice before publishing" (Digital Journalist 2, TV Journalist 3).

"Maybe we didn't think much of it at the time, but subconsciously we were being reserved" (Digital Journalist 2; TV Journalist 4).

4.3. Emotional and psychological impact

Participants described a spectrum of emotional responses, ranging from defiant resilience to profound psychological distress. Some journalists expressed concern not for themselves but for their families, while others reported long-lasting emotional fatigue:

"I wasn't scared for myself, but for my family" (Investigative Journalist 3; TV Journalist 2).

"There were nights I couldn't sleep—my mind was exhausted" (Digital Journalist 4).

A consistent theme across interviews was the spillover of professional stress into family life. Several journalists recounted instances in which their children were bullied at school as a result of social media

campaigns. “My son didn't want to go to school. The comments online were being repeated in the classroom to mock him” (Investigative Journalist 1).

When the police started showing up at our house, and the threats kept coming in relentlessly every day, I said to myself, ‘Enough—I need to step away for a moment.’ It took me an entire month to gather the strength and convince myself that I had to keep going despite the fear and exhaustion. (Investigative Journalist 1).

Despite these intense experiences, none of the participants had sought professional psychological support, citing either distrust in the healthcare system or the social stigma surrounding mental health: “It took me a month to recover emotionally and get back to work” (Investigative Journalist 1).

4.4. Gendered dimensions of mob censorship

The findings indicate that mob censorship affects journalists differently depending on gender. Women reported experiencing more personalized, invasive, and sexualized attacks. One female journalist described an extreme case of symbolic sexual assault via digital platforms:

“After publishing an investigative story, they leaked my private data into online groups that advertised sexual services. I started getting phone calls from men asking for sex. It was two months of horror” (Investigative Journalist 1).

Female journalists frequently experienced sexualized attacks, while male journalists were more often targeted with ideological attacks that focused on their national or religious identity.

Responses from editorial teams varied. Some female journalists reported that sexist attacks were often treated as routine, while some male colleagues perceived no difference in the nature of the harassment:

“They don't address this at all—it's become normal” (Digital Journalist 4).

“Everyone gets attacked the same way. There's no gender difference” (Digital Journalist 6).

These accounts suggest a difference in how harassment is perceived and experienced across genders, with potential implications for newsroom responses and support structures.

5. Discussion

The findings regarding the nature of harassment faced by journalists in Kosovo, addressing the first research question, reveal a complex interplay of digital, political, and gender-based violence. These dynamics produce multifaceted effects, ranging from emotional harm to structural self-censorship, consistent with the concept of mob censorship as a form of “pressure from below” (Waisbord, 2020, 2023). Building on the insights of Waisbord (2020) and Ivask (2025), this study confirms that mob censorship functions as an ecosystem of social pressure in which daily harassment, offensive comments, and online threats collectively generate a climate of fear and uncertainty. Notably, these acts are rarely random; rather, they are often politically and ideologically organized, emanating from interest groups or party militants. This aligns with Claesson's (2023) conceptualization of mob censorship as “taking public space hostage”—a process where digital mob replicate the function of state censorship by inducing self-regulation and selective silence among journalists.

Regarding the second research question, the ambivalent role of newsrooms emerges as a central theme. While editors and colleagues often provide personal and emotional support, newsrooms remain structurally unprepared and insufficiently organized to address mob censorship effectively. Newsrooms generally leave journalists to manage pressures and attacks on their own. In some cases, they even advise journalists not to broadcast or publish certain pieces to avoid potential threats. Although outlets may publicly report that “our journalist was

threatened”, solidarity across newsrooms is limited, and collective responses remain weak. In some instances, threats are normalized as merely “part of the job”, and editors may even recommend removing investigative content to prevent further harassment. Consequently, newsroom support tends to be largely moral rather than material or institutional. The primary mechanism available to journalists is to report incidents to the police and navigate lengthy, bureaucratic legal procedures, leaving them to respond individually. Newsrooms at times appear reluctant to escalate such incidents, particularly when the harassment involves influential political actors, even though these actors have, in some cases, displayed overtly hostile behavior toward the media (European Commission, 2025b).

This finding aligns with Sinclair et al.'s (2025) analysis, which characterizes the journalist as a “sole unit for protection”, internalizing fear as a normalized aspect of the profession. Furthermore, the presence of self-censorship encouraged by newsroom leadership—often manifested in advice to “avoid confrontation” or in statements such as “I was told not to broadcast a certain investigative piece to avoid escalating threats” “we support each other and are not supported by the newsroom”, and “the newsroom rarely provided formal mechanisms for legal assistance”—suggests that newsrooms, to some extent, implicitly tolerate or even institutionalize mob censorship. This illustrates the mechanism of “institutionalized self-censorship” (Sinclair et al., 2025), whereby concerns over the public image and reputation of the news organization translate into explicit or implicit restrictions on journalistic expression. Similar conclusions were reached by Ivask (2025) in Estonia, where newsrooms' institutional indifference normalizes online harassment. This normalization effectively transfers responsibility from the system to the individual journalist, fostering a pervasive culture of fear and self-restraint (Walulya & Selnes, 2023; Waisbord, 2020, 2023).

Journalists described their experiences as emotionally intense, with consequences for sleep, concentration, and family relations. The journalist subjected to doxxing characterized her ordeal as an “emotional collapse” affecting her immediate family. In this context, avoidance of reading hostile comments can be understood as an “avoidance coping” strategy—consciously evading distressing content to preserve professional functionality (Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023). This dimension confirms Claesson's (2023) assertion that mob censorship produces a disembodied, persistent fear that keeps journalists in a state of continuous alarm.

One of the study's most important contributions is its illumination of the gendered dimensions of mob censorship. The data show that harassment is far from gender-neutral: female journalists are subjected to sexualized, objectifying, and moralizing attacks on their bodies, which, as the literature suggests (Malcorps et al., 2023; Miller, 2025), constitute a distinct method of controlling women's voices in the public sphere. Conversely, male journalists primarily endure ideological discrediting through accusations of betrayal or being “foreign mercenaries”. These gendered differences illustrate that harassment operates as a language of power, targeting the most vulnerable aspects of identity—sexuality for women and professional-political authority for men. Consequently, mob censorship emerges as a site where patriarchy and authoritarianism intersect, reinforcing power structures that render journalists—particularly women—vulnerable and isolated. This aligns with Claesson's (2023) and Ivask's (2025) analyses, which view digital public pressure as a surrogate for traditional censorship. The case of the journalist whose personal data were circulated in sexualized online groups exemplifies how mob censorship constitutes gender-based cyber violence with severe psychological and social repercussions. These findings resonate with Walulya and Selnes's (2023) argument that women journalists in small, patriarchal societies face dual vulnerabilities—as critical voices and as targets of gender bias.

Despite the hostile environment created by mob censorship, social media platforms continue to play an essential professional role. Journalists use these platforms to share stories, cultivate sources, and engage audiences, even as toxic content often garners greater engagement

(Henrichsen & Shelton, 2023). This paradox underscores the complexity of social media as both a tool for journalistic work and a vector of harassment.

As a result, targeted online harassment—intended to discredit, delegitimize, and ultimately silence journalists—must be understood as a distinct and evolving form of mob censorship (Bhat & Chadha, 2023).

5.1. Strengths, limitations, and implications

This paper's primary contribution is its empirical investigation of mob censorship in democratic societies, a phenomenon shaped by the digital age. Empirical research on this topic remains limited, reflecting its conceptual novelty, first introduced in 2020 and further defined in 2023 by leading scholars. The findings of this study align closely with the existing empirical literature, reinforcing prior conclusions while adding nuance and depth to the understanding of this emerging phenomenon, as detailed in the Discussion section.

As a near-pioneering effort, the study faces key limitations. First, the absence of a well-established theoretical framework: the literature remains fragmented, leaving structural, psychological, institutional, and historical dimensions under-theorized.

A second limitation is the study's narrow geographical focus. Like other recent qualitative research, this study examines only Kosovo. While this allows for detailed contextual analysis, it limits external validity and the generalizability of the findings. Any broader generalizations must therefore be made cautiously, taking into account differences in political, social, and media environments. The small number of existing empirical studies also restricts opportunities for comparative or meta-analytic verification.

Participant availability and gender balance constitute a limitation. Of the selected journalists, four women and thirteen men participated, while two women declined, slightly reducing the representation of female perspectives. Furthermore, given the sensitive and political nature of the topics, participants' responses may reflect their personal perspectives or experiences, introducing potential bias—an inherent limitation of research relying on human subjects.

Acknowledging these limitations ensures transparency and contextualizes the findings, while pointing to avenues for future research: larger and more diverse samples, cross-national comparisons, mixed-method approaches, and further development of a robust theoretical framework to understand mob censorship as a growing challenge in contemporary democracies.

6. Conclusions

Mob censorship in Kosovo illustrates a shift in control over public discourse from formal institutions to the collective opinion of online users, effectively decentralizing authority while externalizing psychological harm onto journalists. This phenomenon extends beyond increased individual pressure; it fundamentally reshapes journalistic practice by fostering self-censorship and undermining professional autonomy. Interviews reveal that online harassment—often instigated or condoned by political actors—creates a structured form of collective pressure, where fear, fatigue, and anxiety arise not from hierarchical authority but from an online mob exercising moral and emotional control. In this context, journalists' self-censorship functions as a defensive response to socially distributed attacks, transforming the dynamics of control from top-down to bottom-up.

This hybrid form of digital violence, which combines traditional vertical pressures with horizontal mob aggression, is less visible, more diffuse, and therefore harder to challenge, making it potentially more threatening than conventional censorship. Toxic social media environments normalize self-imposed silence through emotional and moral shaming, rendering self-censorship seemingly voluntary when it is in fact collectively imposed.

Practically, these findings underscore the urgent need for integrated

protection strategies, including legal and psychological support, digital security training, and a culture of solidarity within newsrooms. Journalist associations and public institutions must recognize mob censorship as a systemic professional issue rather than an individual problem to be mitigated through silence or restraint. By shifting control over discourse from institutions to collective online opinion, mob censorship compels journalists to self-limit their speech, progressively eroding media independence.

Mob censorship subverts classical top-down models of control, emerging instead from bottom-up, mob-driven dynamics on social media and digital platforms. Its decentralized and collective nature renders it diffuse, largely invisible, and difficult to counter.

Bottom-up censorship is no less—and arguably more—dangerous than traditional forms. It naturalizes fear and frames silence as a rational choice rather than an imposed restriction. Frequently intertwined with political narratives, mob censorship functions as a tool of power, leveraging popular sentiment as a veneer of democratic legitimacy while enforcing control over thought and expression.

In conclusion, in the era of social media democracy, mob censorship represents a significant threat to democratic values: it undermines free speech, encourages self-censorship, and weakens the media's critical role as a check on power. Contemporary censorship operates not through formal bans but via collective emotional and moral pressure, silencing journalists. Protecting journalists from this threat is therefore an ethical, institutional, and democratic imperative to safeguard free expression and independent thought. Despite the hostility of social media environments, these platforms remain indispensable for information dissemination, public engagement, and journalistic visibility—even as toxic content generates disproportionate attention.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Hasan Saliu: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Bujar Tafa:** Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Ethics statement

This study was reviewed and approved by the Central Ethics Commission of AAB College in Kosovo under approval number 814/2025, dated October 20, 2025.

Declaration of the use of AI

The authors declare that no part of the work was generated using AI. AI tools (ChatGPT) were used solely for minor linguistic corrections and vocabulary refinement (e.g., synonyms) in English. After using this tool, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

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